

Comparision of Healing After Gingival Depigmentation following Application of Recombinant Epidermal Growth Factor Gel and Chlorhexidine Containing Gel: A Case Report

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Abstract

Gingival hyperpigmentation is defined as the darkening or discoloration of the gingiva due to excessive deposition of melanin within the basal and suprabasal layers of the gingival epithelium. Gingival depigmentation is a perio-plastic procedure aimed at restoring a lighter gingival appearance; however, it results in a denuded wound that heals by secondary intention and may lead to postoperative pain and discomfort. Topical medicaments are advocated not only to enhance healing and but also for patient comfort. In this present case report, a 23-year-old female patient with deeply pigmented gingiva underwent gingival depigmentation using a ceramic soft tissue trimmer/bur. Postoperatively, the depigmented surgical site was topically applied with REGEN-D® 60 gel on the right side and Hexigel™ on the left side. Clinical evaluations were conducted on the 3rd, 10th, and 30th postoperative days using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) for pain and epithelization tests using hydrogen peroxide and toluidine blue. Both topical agents demonstrated satisfactory healing outcomes and reduction in postoperative discomfort was observed. This case report has shown that REGEN-D® 60 gel has comparatively faster epithelialization, improved angiogenesis, enhanced granulation tissue formation, and greater patient satisfaction.

Introduction

Esthetics plays a vital role in enhancing smile attractiveness and positively influences patient perception, emotional satisfaction, and psychosocial well-being.¹ Gingival hyperpigmentation, caused by excessive melanin deposition in the basal and suprabasal layers of the gingival epithelium, presents an unesthetic appearance that may arise from various physiological or pathological factors.² Gingival depigmentation is a perio-plastic procedure aimed at restoring a lighter, more esthetic gingival appearance, with several modalities available, among which the gingival ceramic trimmer/bur offers effective depigmentation with minimal bleeding, good hemostasis, and enhanced operator control.^{3,4} However, the surgical procedure results in a denuded wound that heals by secondary intention and may cause postoperative pain and discomfort. Topical medicaments play a significant role in promoting healing and reducing post operative infection.

Epidermal Growth Factor (EGF) promotes cell proliferation and wound healing, while oxygen-releasing gels accelerate healing through reduction of free radicals, anti bacterial action, angiogenesis, and re-epithelization of the surgical wound.⁵

Chlorhexidine is considered as the gold standard in the field of nonsurgical periodontal therapy. The topical medicament (Hexigel™) has been significantly used as a part of intraoral medicament. It effectively supports secondary intention healing, reduces bacterial load at the surgical site.⁶

Limited literature has compared a growth factor gel -Recombinant Epidermal Growth Factor Gel (REGEN-D® 60 gel) with gold standard like Chlorhexidine containing gel (Hexigel™) as topical agents following gingival depigmentation. So, the present case report was undertaken to clinically compare their efficacy in accelerating epithelial healing and improving patient satisfaction.

Case Report

A 23-year-old female patient reported to the Department of Periodontics, Institute of Dental Studies and Technologies, Modinagar with a chief complaint of poor esthetics due to the dark pigmented gums. Her oral examination revealed that she had deeply pigmented gingiva from right first premolar to

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left first premolar. The patient requested for any kind of esthetic treatment which could make her “black” coloured gums look better (Figure 1).

Surgical Procedure

The hyperpigmented gingival area was suitably anesthetized with 2% lignocaine hydrochloride with adrenaline 1:80000 after extra-oral disinfection of face around oral cavity and neck with povidone-iodine 5% and intra-oral disinfection with 0.2% chlorhexidine mouth wash. Sterilized ceramic soft tissue trimmer/ bur was utilized on dried gingival area having pigmentation with a high rotary instrumentation (3,00,000-4,50,000 rpm) without water spray. Tissue ablation was started from mucogingival junction and moved in an apico-coronal direction toward the free gingival margin; interdental papillae were included for depigmentation using the overlapping circles and a continuous contact mode, the least amount of pressure, and feather-light brushing strokes avoiding prolonged contact of bur at a single place to prevent removal of large tissue and gingival surface pitting. The entire procedure required extremely controlled pressure and precise expertise. The depigmented site was copiously irrigated using normal saline after completion of surgical procedure (Figure 2). This was followed by division of the ceramic soft tissue bur ablated sextant into two halves (right and left). On the right side Recombinant Epidermal Growth Factor Gel (REGEN-D® 60 gel) was applied while on left side Chlorhexidine containing gel (Hexigel™) was applied (Figure 3). Patient was recalled after 3th, 10th and 30th day for Visual Analogue Scale Score and Epithelization test with H₂O₂ and Toluidine blue (Figure 4 & 5).

Discussion

Gingival depigmentation is a perio-plastic procedure aimed at removing this pigmentation to achieve a lighter and more pleasing gingival appearance and aesthetic appearance.^{1,2} Numerous treatment modalities have been designed for depigmentation including the use of scalpel, chemotherapy, bur abrasion, electrosurgery, cryosurgery, LASER and FGG graft. The soft tissue/gingival ceramic trimmer/ bur is a reliable and satisfactory treatment which includes high rotatory instrumentation without the usage of a water-cooling spray and provides lesser bleeding, adequate hemostasis, minimal thermal damage and improved operator control.

Periodontal dressings and tissue conditioners had been widely used to minimize the patient discomfort, postoperative infection and to enhance healing in cases of gingival depigmentation. Application of any topical obtunding medicament onto the exposed surgical site aids in the post-surgical healing thus reducing occurrence of an infection.⁷

In the present case report, both the materials were comparable in all the aspect but REGEN-D® 60 gel was intended to improve wound healing by promoting angiogenesis, epidermal cell regeneration, formation of granulation tissue as well as increasing the motility of fibroblasts.⁸ According to Buckley A et al⁸, Laato M et al⁹, application of different formulations of epidermal growth factors onto experimentally induced open wounds improves epithelization with simultaneously accumulating granulation tissue. Brown GL et al¹⁰ also promote the application of epidermal growth factor gel as it plays a significant role in healing of open surgical wounds.

However, Chlorhexidine (CHX) incorporated gel-based

dressing also resulted in rapid wound healing due to less accumulation of plaque which maintains the anti-bacterial environment around the surgical site.¹¹ This was supported by Bakaeen GS et al¹¹ who compared the effects of 1% CHX and Placebo gels during the healing phase following mucogingival flap surgery.

Conclusion

REGEN-D®-60 gel and Hexigel™ both contribute effectively to better healing and diminished post-operative discomfort after gingival depigmentation. Clinically Recombinant Epidermal Growth Factor Gel (REGEN-D®-60 gel) has been proved as an excellent therapeutic modality for topical application of open intraoral surgical wounds. The ability of accelerated epidermal growth and differentiation, reduced healing time and enhanced patient satisfaction make (REGEN-D®-60 gel to be treatment of choice for surgical depigmented sites.

Figure 1: Bur Tip At Hyperpigmented Site

Figure 2: Surgical Site After Soft Tissue Ceramic Bur Ablation

(a) (b) Figure 3: Application Of Gel

3rd Day Recall 10th Day Recall 30th Day Recall Figure 4: Epithelization Test By Hydrogen Peroxide

3rd Day Recall

10th Day Recall

30th Day Recall

Figure 5: Epithelization by Toluidine Blue

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